

Special Relativity and the laws of Physics

Khaled M. Khaled

Department of Physics, Zagazig University, Egypt

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Abstract

Special relativity represents a novel perspective on space and time as two interdependent quantities in which the speed of light is the maximum speed in the universe, and all the laws of physics are invariant in all inertial frames, and we investigated whether we can mathematically demonstrate that. In this article we tried to show the modifications in some laws of physics to be consistent with this modern perspective, moreover we examined if all the laws of physics are the same in all inertial frames by setting the left-hand side and the right-hand side of the law in tensor form and finding whether both of them transform according to the Lorentz transformation matrix or not. It was found that the laws of classical mechanics and electrodynamics and consequently may all the laws of physics have the same form in all inertial systems.

1 Introduction

The speeds that we experience in the macroscopic world are much lower than the speed of light. for example, a car moving with speed of 200 km/h or sound waves that spread in air with speed of $3.43 \times 10^2 \text{ m/s}$, These speeds are not comparable to the speed of light $c = 3 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}$.

$$\frac{\sim 10^2}{\sim 10^8} = 10^{-6} \cong 0$$

On the other hand, in the microscopic scale, we can find a particle moving at a speed comparable to the speed of light, such as the electron in Bohr's first orbit in the hydrogen atom moving at the speed of $2.2 \times 10^6 \text{ m/s}$, or accelerated elementary particles can approach the speed of light.

In classical mechanics, there is no upper limit to the speeds of objects under study, and hence the speed of light is not a crucial constant. Thus, if two particles are going toward each other at a speed of $0.7 c$, then it is classically accepted that each one observes the other with speed equals $1.4 c$, which is normally calculated by the Galilean velocity addition theorem, causing the resultant speed to exceed the speed of light. However, it was found experimentally that accelerated elementary particles cannot exceed the speed of light, regardless of their acceleration energy.

Measurements show that, if an electron is accelerated by 10 MeV , it was found to have a speed of $0.9988 c$. Classically, since any type of energies must be directly proportional to the square of the corresponding speed, it was classically expected that, if the acceleration energy is fourfold, the velocity will be doubled to $1.9976 c$, whereas it was found experimentally to be $0.9999 c$.

Furthermore, if an electron is set in a magnetic field of 2 T flux density and is accelerated by 10 MeV , classically the orbit radius must be 0.53 cm , where the Larmor radius is classically calculated as

$$r = \frac{\sqrt{2m K}}{qB}$$

But the practical result was about 1.75 cm [1], therefore it follows that classical mechanics is limited only for speeds much lower than the speed of light; hence we can conclude that Newtonian mechanics is a special case of a more generalized theory, which is Einstein's special theory of relativity which is analogous to quantum mechanics that describes systems of spatial dimensions much smaller than that of our macroscopic world.

Now, there must be some corrections under the circumstances of speeds comparable to the speed of light, which will depend on a new perspective of space and time under the constancy of the speed of light, and set it to be the upper limit on speeds in the universe. Furthermore, it is logical that the relativistic effect is extended to electrodynamics, where the whole idea is dependent on the features of the speed of light, which is basically electromagnetic radiation.

The aim of this article is to cover different aspects such as kinematics, dynamics, and electrodynamics in the framework that describe them well at extremely high speeds, which is special relativity, showing a novel perspective about them at these high speeds and proving that all the laws of physics are invariant from a frame to another under the Lorentz transformation.

2 Background on special relativity

Classically, any event in a moving inertial frame S' with respect to another frame S is fully specified by four coordinates, three for space and one for time (t, x, y, z) . Where, the inertial frame is the frame that obeys Newton's law of inertia (Newton's first law) by moving with a uniform velocity, where acceleration effect is absent.

Hence, for any body subjected to zero net force, it will be observed by another observer in another frame to move with a constant velocity, in a straight line since its frame of reference is not accelerating. Classically, the fundamental physical quantities, length, time, and mass, are absolute quantities, i.e., if two identical bodies are at rest in their spatial dimensions and mass, containing two synchronized clocks, they must "classically" remain identical in all of these quantities even if they are compared under a relative motion to each other, where the measurement must be at the same time[1].

It follows that the components of the acceleration of the moving body are the same for the two frames since we are considering inertial frames, and as stated previously, the mass of the moving body is invariant under the relative motion.

Hence the Newtonian second law is classically invariant in all inertial frames

$$a'_x = a_x \quad , \quad a'_y = a_y \quad , \quad a'_z = a_z$$

$$\therefore F' = F$$

And by subordination, all equations of motion and conservation laws are the same in all frames [2]; then we can say that all the laws of mechanics are the same in all inertial frames, even under the variation of the numerical values of the physical quantities.

2.1 Galilean transformations

If an event takes place in a point (t', x', y', z') in an inertial frame S' that is moving with a uniform velocity v in the x direction relative to another frame S , for an observer in the second frame, the event is at the point (t, x, y, z)

Figure 1: Galilean transformations representation

then:

$$x = x' + vt' \quad , \quad y = y' \quad , \quad z = z' \quad , \quad t = t'$$

$$\therefore u = u' + v \quad \text{and} \quad a = a'$$

Therefore, according to the Galilean transformations [2], if a photon is emitted in an inertial frame moving with speed v with respect to another frame in the same direction as the frame's motion, that photon can be observed by an observer in the other frame with speed $c' = c + v$, and that violates Maxwell's assumption that the speed of electromagnetic radiation has a constant value for each medium and is calculated as $c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mu\epsilon}}$, thus it was expected, the laws of electrodynamics such as Maxwell's equations are not retaining their form under Galilean transformations unlike the laws of classical mechanics, and that may be due to incorrect formalism of Maxwell's electrodynamics relations, in correct forms of classical mechanics, or there is a hypothetical preferred frame for the laws of electrodynamics in which only the laws of electrodynamics are correct, which is said to be the ether frame.

Experimentally, it is observed that there is no violation in the laws of electrodynamics, and by ruling out the ether hypothesis as shown in later sections, the only remaining possibility is that the laws of classical mechanics must be generalized to account for extremely high velocities and the modern nature of space and time [1].

2.2 The ether hypothesis

Mechanical waves such as sound waves need a medium to propagate through, for example, sound waves propagate in dry air with speed 343 m/s, which is the relative velocity of the sound wave with respect to a stationary air mass. By symmetry, a hypothetical medium was proposed for electromagnetic radiation to propagate through, which is a preferred rest frame for electromagnetic radiation called the ether, which has zero density, fixed with respect to the sun and totally transparent.

Since the ether is supposed to be the medium in which light propagates, the absolute speed of light with respect to the ether has to be c , and it is assumed that if a light photon is moving relative to an observer moving with speed v with respect to the ether, the observer will observe the photon moving with speed c' varying between $c - v$ and $c + v$, for that reason the Michelson-Morley experiment was established to test the possibility of the change in the value of the speed of light due to the relative motion, and verifying the ether hypothesis [1].

2.3 Michelson-Morley experiment

Its basic idea depends on the use of the Michelson interferometer to observe the change in the interference pattern between two light beams passing through two different paths with essentially two different velocities with respect to the hypothetical ether. Where, if the setup shown in figure 2 is rotated through 90° , the two beams will swap the paths causing a shifted interference pattern due to the change in the phase relation between the two beams.

Figure 2: Michelson-Morley experiment setup

In the horizontal path from the transparent mirror to the first fully reflective mirror, the photons will move through the same distance L with different values of relative velocities back and forth relative to that hypothetical medium.

Then, the total path time of the horizontal trip will be

$$t_1 = \frac{L}{c - v} + \frac{L}{c + v} = \frac{2L}{c} \left(\frac{1}{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right)$$

On the other hand, in the vertical path, photons will travel the up and down trips with the same resultant speed of photons and the moving setup relative to the ether in a time interval $t_2 = \frac{2L}{c} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \right)$; hence the time span between vertical and horizontal trips is:

$$\Delta t = L \frac{v^2}{c^3}$$

And the path difference will be

$$\delta = L \frac{v^2}{c^2}$$

Which will “theoretically” cause a phase shift.

Figure 3: Vertical path of Michelson-Morley experiment

After applying the experiment under various conditions, the theoretical expected shift in the pattern was not observed at all, which strongly challenged the ether hypothesis. This experimental fact can be interpreted as meaning that the speed of light is a universal constant which is independent of the direction of motion or the state of the emitting body, hence there is no need to postulate a hypothetical preferred frame for electromagnetic radiation to propagate through. Furthermore, the speed of the light beam in all directions in the Michelson-Morley experiment must be the same rather than varying in the interval between $c - v$ and $c + v$, which is a crucial violation of the Galilean intuition of the relative velocity, leading to the origin of a new theory dealing with space and time as relative quantities instead of being absolute, only to make the speed of light treat as a universal constant [1].

As the speed of light was concluded to be a universal constant in all inertial frames, the laws of electrodynamics must be invariant in all inertial frames, not only the laws of classical mechanics [1], but by symmetry the conservation must be expanded to all the laws of physics. From the preceding discussion, Einstein concluded the two basic postulates of his theory of relativity which are stated as:

1. All the laws of physics have the same form in all inertial frames (no absolute rest frame).
2. The speed of light is an absolute constant in all directions and in all frames regardless of the motion of the source (there is no ether), which is itself a law of physics.

Hence, we must think about the revisions of the laws of physics which preserve the constancy of the speed of light and to be the upper limit of all velocities in the universe. Furthermore, to test these modifications to see if they will keep the same form for all inertial frames or not, and whether they reduce to the classical forms at sufficiently low speeds [3].

3 Relativistic Kinematics

As we know, kinematics describes the motion of an object, regardless of the reason of this motion, hence it mainly focuses on position and time, according to the novel perspective of space and time in special relativity, we must introduce new ideas about space and time, such as length contraction, simultaneity, and time dilation.

3.1 Relativity of simultaneity

If two photons are sent from the midpoint between two detectors in a moving system, they will propagate at the same speed in opposite directions. Therefore, for an observer within that frame, the two photons will be detected simultaneously.

Conversely, for an observer in the stationary frame, the two events will not be simultaneous, where the back edge photon has to travel a shorter distance than the frontal one, but of course, in order to detect this relativistic effect, the speed of the moving inertial system has to be comparable to the speed of the moving signal or object; hence the relativity of simultaneity is negligible for photons in the low-speed systems compared to the speed of light, such as in a moving train.

Figure 4: Simple representation for relativity of simultaneity

3.2 Time dilation

If we throw a projectile up in a moving train and observe its motion until returning to its origin, for an observer on the train, it moves in a linear path up and down.

On the other hand, for an observer outside the train, it moved in a parabolic trajectory, which is clearly longer than the linear path, although the event started and ended at the same instant for the two observers, and that can be obviously explained by the relative velocity of the projectile due to the moving train.

Figure 5: Different paths of a classical projectile relative to different observers

What if the same experiment is performed for a light photon instead of a classical object, according to the basic postulates of special relativity, the speed of light is a universal constant, and it is clear for us that the light photon for the two observers took two different paths of different lengths, which of course leads to different traveling times observed by each observer, which results in time dilation for the moving frame.

Figure 6: Different paths of a light signal relative to different observers

$$\Delta t_o = \frac{h}{c} \quad , \quad \Delta t = \frac{\sqrt{h^2 + (v\Delta t)^2}}{c}$$

$$\Delta t = \frac{h}{c} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

$$\Delta t = \gamma \Delta t_o \tag{1}$$

Time dilation has the most persuasive confirmation among the three predictions under study, which was practically indicated from the comparison between the lifetime of elementary particles at rest and their real lifetime when they are moving with speeds comparable to the speed of light, as they last for much longer time, according to the particle system it behaves as if it is at rest, whereas it is moving at a very high speed relative to an observer in a laboratory, and that fits well with the calculations of relativity.

Furthermore, an experiment was performed in which scientists used different atomic clocks due to their high accuracy, calculated the variation in time intervals between a stationary clock on earth and two clocks aboard an aircraft, one in the same direction of earth's rotation about its axis, and the other in the opposite direction[4].

The calculations of time dilation for the two relative motions supported the prediction of time dilation.

According to the time dilation, the twin paradox was introduced, which can also help us understand that this prediction is not a mistake arising from a failure to calculate the traveled time, but it is indeed a change in the nature of time to be slower in the moving observed frame, and this effect extends to the biological processes leading to this paradox.

3.3 Length contraction

Imagine a performed experiment in a moving train car to a light photon directed horizontally to a mirror away by distance L_o from the source and reflected back again to its starting point.

Figure 7: Different trajectories of a light photon relative to different observers

for an observer in the train car, the total traveled distance is $2L_o$, therefore, the trip period is calculated as:

$$\Delta t_o = \frac{2L_o}{c} \quad (2)$$

on the other hand, for an observer for which the train is moving with a relative velocity v , the time of the coming and going trips varies from each other, where:

$$\Delta t_1 = \frac{L + v\Delta t_1}{c} \quad i.e. \quad \Delta t_1 = \frac{L}{c - v}$$

$$\Delta t_2 = \frac{L - v\Delta t_2}{c} \quad i.e. \quad \Delta t_2 = \frac{L}{c + v}$$

$$\Delta t = t_1 + t_2 = \frac{2L}{c} \gamma^2 \quad (3)$$

By solving 1 and 2 in 3:

$$L_o = \gamma L \tag{4}$$

which reduces to the classical relation at sufficiently low speeds, and shows that the measured lengths vary under the effect of special relativity by the same factor causing time dilation, where the measured length in the same direction of motion of a non-inertial frame from a different frame is observed to be shorter than being measured from the same frame, but components perpendicular to the direction of motion are not affected.

Unlike time dilation, there is no experimental evidence on the length contraction, but mathematics predicts this effect.

Then, in a brief, we can say, according to the postulates of relativity we face new intuitions for space and time, leading to changes in their measured values by different observers in different frames, where the clocks in a moving frame run slower and objects within that frame are shortened along the direction of motion. Furthermore, if two events are simultaneous in an inertial frame, they are not necessarily simultaneous in another.

3.4 Four-vector

Analogous to the three-vector which is a set of three components that can have an invariant magnitude under any rotation of the system, in relativity we have defined the 4-vector [3], which is a new concept that arises due to the novel perspective of space and time, in which we deal with them as a unit not two separate objects, where the four-vector is any set of four components that transfers in the same way as the spacetime coordinates under Lorentz transformations such that it has an invariant spacetime norm in order to keep the speed of light the same in all inertial frames.

In the three-dimensional space, if the left-hand side and the right-hand side are the same type, vectors or scalars, and both rotate the same way under spatial rotations, the equation is said to be rotationally invariant. Analogous to this, in the four-dimensional world (spacetime), if the left-hand side and the right-hand side are four-vectors, and both transform the same way under Lorentz transformations, the law is said to be Lorentz covariant, which provides a simple way to prove that all the laws of physics are the same in all inertial frames.

3.5 Lorentz transformation equations and position four vector

Lorentz transformation relations are a modulation to the Galilean relations by some factor depending on the velocity [2] such as:

$$x = f(v)(x' + vt') \tag{5}$$

$$x' = f(v)(x - vt) \tag{6}$$

and we have:

$$x = ct \tag{7}$$

$$x' = ct' \tag{8}$$

by solving 6 in 5 and 8 in 7, this modification factor was found to be the same relativistic factor mentioned earlier ($f(v) = \gamma$) and a temporal equation was expressed as:

$$t = \gamma(t' + \frac{x'v}{c^2}) \quad (9)$$

and the reversed equation is:

$$t' = \gamma(t - \frac{xv}{c^2}) \quad (10)$$

the components normal to the direction of motion will not experience any changes:

$$y = y' \quad , \quad z = z' \quad (11)$$

Conventionally, we will keep time to have the same dimension of space; by multiplying it to be the speed of light

$$x = \gamma(x' + \beta ct') \quad (12)$$

and the reversed equation is:

$$x' = \gamma(x - \beta ct) \quad (13)$$

and the temporal relations will be:

$$ct = \gamma(ct' + \frac{x'v}{c}) \quad (14)$$

$$ct' = \gamma(ct - \frac{xv}{c}) \quad (15)$$

Hence, Lorentz transformation equations can be set in a compact matrix[3] as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} ct' \\ x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \gamma & -\beta\gamma & 0 & 0 \\ -\beta\gamma & \gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} ct \\ x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix}$$

where $\beta = \frac{v}{c}$ and these relations reduce to the Galilean at low speeds. this transformation is simply given as:

$$X'^{\mu} = \Lambda_{\nu}^{\mu} X^{\nu} \quad (16)$$

where the transformation matrix is called Lorentz matrix Λ_{ν}^{μ} , and we call the set of spacetime coordinates, $X'^{\mu} = (ct', x', y', z')$, the position-four vector, which tells us where and when an event occurs relative to the origin of a reference frame, and it has an invariant spacetime norm in all inertial frames called spacetime interval [3].

3.6 Spacetime interval

In the Euclidean coordinates, under the rotation of the system we have varying coordinates for each point, but there is an invariant quantity, namely the Euclidean distance, as it has the same value under the rotation of the coordinates.

Analogous to this, in special relativity under Lorentz transformation of a spacetime system, we have different values of spatial and temporal coordinates, but there is an invariant quantity, so called the spacetime interval [3], which must be invariant under the Lorentz transformation in order to keep the speed of light a universal constant for all observers in all systems, where:

$$\Delta s^2 = (c\Delta t)^2 - \Delta x^2 - \Delta y^2 - \Delta z^2 \quad (17)$$

For simplicity, let us focus on only one spatial component:

$$\Delta s^2 = (c\Delta t)^2 - \Delta x^2 \quad (18)$$

It is obvious from the relation that the spacetime interval is referring to the distance in the 4-dimensional universe as it depends on both position and time as shown, where in relativity the space and time are interdependent, unlike in classical physics, and that is clear shown from the Lorentz transformation relations (5 and 9).

For photons, since $(c\Delta t)^2 = \Delta x^2$, then the spacetime interval must always be zero, and generally invariant quantity under the Lorentz transformation:

$$(c\Delta t)^2 - \Delta x^2 = (c\Delta t')^2 - \Delta x'^2$$

The form of the spacetime interval relation indicates that the points of the same value of spacetime interval on the spacetime diagram are represented on a hyperbola not a circle like length in the Euclidean coordinate system, which is called the calibration curve, as for any point on it, they have the same spacetime interval value, and is represented geometrically as:

$$\cosh^2\Phi - \sinh^2\Phi = 1 \quad (19)$$

Figure 8: Spacetime interval calibration curve

From 18 and 19:

$$ct = s \cosh\Phi \quad , \quad x = s \sinh\Phi$$

hence:

$$\tanh\Phi = \beta \quad , \quad \cosh\Phi = \gamma$$

Hence, another form of Lorentz transformation matrix concerning the hyperbolic functions is

$$\begin{pmatrix} ct' \\ x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cosh\Phi & -\sinh\Phi & 0 & 0 \\ -\sinh\Phi & \cosh\Phi & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} ct \\ x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix}$$

by solving ct' , x' , y' and z' expressed from this matrix into the primed version of 18, we obtain the RHS of the unprimed version, proving that the spacetime interval is an invariant quantity.

3.7 Minkowski spacetime diagram

If a system is moving with velocity v relative to another one, the origin of this system will have a worldline in the stationary system, where the worldline represents the progress of an object in the spacetime diagram [1], and its slope is the inverse of its velocity, hence, for a stationary object, worldline must be parallel to the time axis of its reference frame.

Figure 9: Minkowski spacetime diagram

Where the time axis in the primed frame is satisfying the equation $x' = 0$, by the substitution in 13, then we get:

$$ct = \frac{1}{\beta}x$$

and the x' axis will satisfy the equation $t' = 0$, and from 15, then we obtain:

$$ct = \beta x$$

and that shows the deformation in spacetime of a moving frame relative to another one, causing in the new thoughts of spacetime physics by the new consideration of the axes.

3.7.1 Relativity of simultaneity on Minkowski spacetime diagram

Let us consider four different events, E_1 , E_2 , E'_1 and E'_2 .

We say that two events are simultaneous if they both take place at the same instant, and to determine the time of occurrence for some event within a coordinate system we get a line parallel to the position axis and identify the time intercept.

From this, it is clear that the two events E_1 and E_2 are simultaneous in S but separated in S' .

On the other hand, the two events E'_1 and E'_2 are simultaneous in S' but separated in S .

Figure 10: Illustration of the relativity of simultaneity on Minkowski spacetime diagram

3.7.2 Length contraction on Minkowski spacetime diagram

Let us assume a meter stick of length L_o to be at rest with respect to S' , to measure the length we get the separation of the two end points simultaneously, and to obtain its length geometrically with respect to this system, it will be the separation between the worldlines of the two end points on that system, which is the distance between the intersections of the two worldlines with the x-axis or any other parallel line.

It is clear geometrically that by following these steps in the two systems, the length is contracted in S , as previously obtained mathematically. The reciprocal nature of this can be obtained by inverting our point of view, where the meter stick is set at rest relative to the frame S , by the same way of detecting the length corresponding to each system, it is clear that the S' frame observer will observe it to be contracted.

Figure 11: Illustration of Length contraction on Minkowski spacetime diagram

But a great observation on the spacetime diagram to call here is that S' observer will detect it moving to the left, and that is due to the relative detection of velocities between the two systems.

3.7.3 Time dilation on Minkowski spacetime diagram

Suppose a stationary clock C' is placed in the moving system S' ticking off units of time, whose worldline is shown parallel to the time axis of its inertial system. By using the same concept of length measurement to obtain the time intervals in both the primed and the unprimed system, it becomes clear that the observer in the frame S will measure a longer time interval.

On the other hand, by studying the reciprocal case, in which the clock C will be stationary with respect to the system S , and plotting its worldline, it follows that the observer in S' will observe the time to be dilated.

Figure 12: Illustration of time dilation on Minkowski spacetime diagram

3.8 Cause and Effect

From figure 9, the worldline of light have slope of one on the spacetime diagram, and for any material object, it must has a greater slope, where ($v < c$). Furthermore, we can get the square of the spacetime interval magnitude by the 4-vector dot product, which is like the known dot product except adding different signs for the spatial and temporal component, hence we need the Minkowski matrix:

$$s^2 = \eta_{\mu\nu} X^\mu X^\nu \quad \text{and suppose conventionally that} \quad \eta_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

then, we obtain $s^2 = (ct)^2 - x^2 - y^2 - z^2$

If its value is negative, that is an indication that the the spatial components dominate, hence we call it space-like, which means that the change in position between an event A at origin and any other event B is greater than the change in the temporal component.

On the other hand, if its value is positive, that means that the dominant change is in the temporal component, not the spatial components, hence it is called time-like, which means that the change in position between an event A at the origin and any other event B is lower than the change in the time component. If it is zero, it is called light-like.

As mentioned before, the photons have a spacetime interval of zero, furthermore, it is an indication that the change in the space and time components are the same and cancel each other, and that occurs if and only if the connection between the two events makes a tilt angle of 45° with both time and space axis, and that coincides with the photons worldline.

If an observer at event A starts at rest for simplicity, and of course it has a velocity lower than the speed of light, and 3 other events B' , B'' and B''' , lying in its forward light cone (its future), on the light worldline and out of the light cone respectively.

The spacetime interval between them must be positive, zero, and negative respectively as they are time-like, light-like, and space-like respectively.

Figure 13: The causal effect on the light cone

If we think about it from a different perspective, for a negative spacetime interval (space-like), it is possible to get the time interval between the two events to be zero, then they have the possibility to be simultaneous, therefore neither event can causally influence the other.

On the other hand, a positive spacetime interval (time-like) indicates that it is possible to have a time interval between the two events of a non-zero value, hence it is possible for one of them to cause the other.

Moreover, the worldline between the two events indicates that the transition is faster than the speed of light, which violates the second postulate of special relativity, and would lead to imaginary values in the Lorentz factor, which is unphysical. Then, event A always has the possibility to cause B' where the time order is well-defined within the timelike region and cannot be reversed.

Event A can cause event B'' if and only if it is caused by any massless signal, such as electromagnetic radiation. In short, displacement between causally related events cannot be space-like, and their ordering is the same for all inertial observers [3].

3.9 Velocity four vector

If an observer is calculating the ordinary velocity of a moving object in the spacetime, it will be the rate of change of the particle position detected by the observer with respect to the time of the observer:

$$v = \frac{d}{dt}(ct, x, y, z) = (c, v_x, v_y, v_z)$$

On the other hand, if the rate of change is with respect to the time of the particle itself (proper time), we obtain the proper velocity, which is clear to be a hybrid quantity, and to be the relativistic version of the ordinary velocity:

$$\frac{d}{dt_o}(ct, x, y, z) = \frac{d}{dt\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}(ct, x, y, z) = \gamma v$$

We can compress the components of the proper velocity four-vector[3] to be:

$$U^\mu = (u^0, u^1, u^2, u^3) \tag{20}$$

As we mentioned before, the four-vector obeys a specific transformation matrix from one frame to another. Also, the proper velocity four-vector must transfer the same way of position four-vector transformation following the Lorentz matrix.

From the first derivative of 11, 13 and 15 with respect to the proper time we get:

$$u'^0 = \gamma(u^0 - \beta u^1) \tag{21}$$

$$u'^1 = \gamma(u^1 - \beta u^0) \tag{22}$$

$$u'^2 = u^2, \quad u'^3 = u^3$$

which can be expressed in the matrix form as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} u'^0 \\ u'^1 \\ u'^2 \\ u'^3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \gamma & -\beta\gamma & 0 & 0 \\ -\beta\gamma & \gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u^0 \\ u^1 \\ u^2 \\ u^3 \end{pmatrix}$$

which has the compact form of $U'^{\mu} = \Lambda^{\mu}_{\nu} U^{\nu}$ Since the vector 20 obeying Lorentz transformation matrix, it indeed can be defined as the proper velocity four-vector, which has the same magnitude in all frames $c^2 = \eta_{\mu\nu} U^{\mu} U^{\nu}$.

3.10 Addition of velocities theorem

Classically, according to the Galilean velocity addition theorem [2], if a body is moving with a velocity u' in an inertial frame of reference S' , which is moving with a velocity v relative to another frame S , the observer in S will observe the object moving with a relative velocity u equals the vector summation of the two velocities:

$$u = v + u'$$

which is clear to be limited for low speeds since it violates the second postulate of special relativity at high speeds.

On the other hand, since the velocity is generally expressed as $u' = \frac{dx'}{dt'}$, Einstein used the first derivative of Lorentz transformation relations, and substituted in this general relation, getting the conclusion to his velocity addition theorem[2] to be:

$$u' = \frac{u - v}{1 - \frac{uv}{c^2}}, \quad u = \frac{u' + v}{1 + \frac{u'v}{c^2}}$$

which fits well with the second postulate of special relativity, even if we set the velocity of the moving body to be c , the observer in the frame S will observe its velocity to be c , where the speed of light in special relativity is the analogous value to the infinite velocity in classical mechanics.

Although the frame is moving only in the x-axis direction, the moving body can move in all directions causing additional displacements in y and z components. suppose that displacements in y' and z' to be dy' and dz' respectively, and the time interval to be dt' hence, the velocity component in the y' and z' axis directions are:

$$u'_y = \frac{u_y \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{1 - \frac{vu_x}{c^2}}, \quad u'_z = \frac{u_z \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{1 - \frac{vu_x}{c^2}}$$

And will be detected in the frame S as:

$$u_y = \frac{u'_y \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{1 + \frac{vu'_x}{c^2}}, \quad u_z = \frac{u'_z \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{1 + \frac{vu'_x}{c^2}}$$

Notice that these relations reduce to Galilean velocity addition theorem at low speeds.

4 Relativistic Dynamics

Dynamics aims to study the cause of motion; hence it extends to cover some concepts such as energy, momentum and forces acting on the moving object, thus we tend to cover these aspects from the new context of special relativity.

4.1 Energy-momentum four vector

Momentum on its classical form $p = mv$ was not conserved in all inertial frames, until being modulated by the relativistic factor γ , then it will be the rest mass multiplied by the proper velocity:

$$p = \gamma mv$$

hence it can be set in the four-vector form as:

$$P^\mu = \gamma mv^\mu = mU^\mu = \left(\frac{E}{c}, p_x, p_y, p_z\right)$$

or it can be written as:

$$P^\mu = (p^0, p^1, p^2, p^3) \quad (23)$$

It follows that the spatial components represent the momentum, while the temporal component corresponds to the relativistic total energy, as derived from Einstein's most famous mass-energy equivalence relation.

Since the momentum four-vector[3] is obtained by multiplying an invariant quantity (the rest mass) by the proper velocity four-vector 20, which transforms according to the Lorentz transformation matrix as shown previously, the momentum four-vector must also obey the same transformation rule, thereby proving that it is a four-vector.

$$mU'^\mu = \Lambda_\nu^\mu mU^\nu$$

$$P'^\mu = \Lambda_\nu^\mu P^\nu$$

As mentioned in the kinematics section, velocity can be expressed in four-vector form. Now, we have shown that momentum is also a four-vector quantity. Therefore, both sides of the relativistic momentum relation are of the same type (four-vectors), and applying the Lorentz transformation matrix to both sides yields the corresponding momentum relation in the primed frame.

$$\Lambda_\nu^\mu P^\nu = \Lambda_\nu^\mu mU^\nu$$

$$P'^\mu = mU'^\mu$$

which indicates that this law has the same form in all inertial frames. moreover, momentum will have an invariant norm in all frames calculated as:

$$m^2 c^2 = \eta_{\mu\nu} P^\mu P^\nu = \frac{E^2}{c^2} - p^2$$

which leads to the energy-momentum relation:

$$E^2 = m^2 c^4 + p^2 c^2 \quad (24)$$

which is reduced to the rest mass-energy relation $E = mc^2$ for a body of zero momentum, and leads to the energy of the mass less particles to be calculated as $E = pc$. since the energy of photons for example is calculated as $E = h\nu$, by solving the two equations we obtain the de Broglie wave-particle duality relation $p = \frac{h}{\lambda}$, which is the gateway to the quantum world.

4.2 Force

The generalized form of the Newtonian second law is that the force is the rate of change of the momentum of an object, then the force component of the same velocity direction under the relativity effect will be:

$$F = \frac{dp}{dt} = m \frac{d(\gamma v)}{dt}$$

Then, the force relativistic form[2] will end up as follows:

$$F = ma\gamma^3$$

this relation reduces to the classical form at relatively low velocities, additionally, it indicates that we need to apply an infinite amount of force on the moving object to reach the speed of light, which is impossible.

Figure 14: Classical and relativistic force as a function of velocity

Furthermore, we can use the relation between force and momentum in relativity to investigate the position and velocity of a relativistic moving particle as a function of time

$$dp = f \cdot dt$$

Let for simplicity, the particle starts its motion at rest affected by a constant force (acceleration) then:

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma m v &= f t \\ \therefore v &= \frac{f t}{m} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \end{aligned}$$

which is the velocity of the particle in the lab frame.
By rearrangement:

$$v = \frac{\frac{f t}{m}}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{f t}{m c}\right)^2}}$$

which indeed indicate that the particle starts at rest, for a small time interval of motion, the relation will be reduced under the binomial approximation to:

$$v = \frac{f t}{m} \left(1 - \frac{f^2 t^2}{2 m^2 c^2}\right) \quad , \quad \text{where, } f = \frac{m v}{t}$$

by substitution, it indeed will keep the same velocity value with no relativistic effect.

Finally, for time goes to infinity, the velocity will have its upper most value which is the speed of light.

hence, the velocity characteristics of a moving particle under a constant velocity as a function of time will be linear at first such as classical case, then starts to concave at relatively high speeds, and finally is saturated at the speed of light [3].

Figure 15: Illustration of classical and relativistic velocities as a function of time

$$\therefore v = \frac{\frac{ft}{m}}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{ft}{mc}\right)^2}}$$

$$\therefore dx = \frac{\frac{ft}{m}}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{ft}{mc}\right)^2}} dt$$

by integration we get:

$$x = \frac{mc^2}{f} \left(\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{ft}{mc}\right)^2} - 1 \right)$$

which will reduce under the binomial approximation at short time interval of motion to the classical case, following a parabolic behavior at first

$$x = \frac{ft^2}{2m}$$

Since the speed of light will strictly be the higher allowed velocity, the curve later becomes linear[3], and if we conventionally set the time axis to be ct , the tilt angel of this linear curve must be 45° .

Figure 16: Classical and relativistic variation in position as a function of time

4.3 Force four-vector

Since force is the rate of change of momentum, to get the force four-vector [3], we must find the rate of change of the momentum four-vector with respect to the proper time of the moving particle.

$$\therefore F = \frac{dp}{dt_o} = \gamma \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{E}{c}, p_x, p_y, p_z \right)$$

Which we can be set in a compact form as:

$$F^\mu = (F^0, F^1, F^2, F^3) \quad (25)$$

Where it is clear that the temporal component corresponds to power, and the spatial components refer to the force components.

Since we previously proved that momentum is a four-vector obeys the Lorentz transformation, and force is the rate of change of momentum with respect to an invariant quantity (the proper time), force is also a four-vector obeying the Lorentz transformation matrix:

$$\begin{aligned} P'^\mu &= \Lambda^\mu_\nu P^\nu \\ \frac{d}{dt_o} P'^\mu &= \Lambda^\mu_\nu \frac{d}{dt_o} P^\nu \\ \therefore F'^\mu &= \Lambda^\mu_\nu F^\nu \end{aligned}$$

5 Relativistic Electrodynamics

According to Galilean transformations, if a charge is placed at rest in a moving frame S' with a uniform velocity v with respect to another frame S , for an observer in the primed system the charge is associated only with its electric field, with no magnetic field present. On the other hand; for an observer in the frame S , the charge is moving with a relative velocity v , therefore, it is associated with both electric and magnetic fields.

Figure 17: Illustration of the Galilean point of view about electric and magnetic fields

If we have a look at the Maxwell's relations in their classical differential form:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = \frac{\rho}{\varepsilon_0} \quad (26)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad (27)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \quad (28)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \mu_0 \mathbf{J} + \mu_0 \varepsilon_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} \quad (29)$$

It follows that these equations describe all electromagnetic phenomena. The first equation refers to the electric field associated with static charges, while the second describes the behavior of magnetic field lines and implies the nonexistence of magnetic monopoles. The third and fourth equations together show that time-varying electric and magnetic fields sustain one another, leading to the formation of a self-propagating electromagnetic wave. Solving these equations in vacuum yields the wave equation that describes electromagnetic waves propagating in vacuum.

where, the equation 28 can be set as:

$$\nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \nabla \times \mathbf{B}$$

from vector calculus it can be constructed as:

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{E} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \nabla \times \mathbf{B}$$

by substitution using equation 29 in vacuum we get:

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{E} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \mathbf{E} = 0$$

which is the wave equation of the electric field component of an electromagnetic signal. As mentioned earlier, under the Galilean transformations, different observers have different thoughts about electric and magnetic fields, hence Maxwell's relations will not be covariant under the Galilean transformations, and since Maxwell's equations are the cornerstone of electrodynamics, the changing in their form under the Galilean transformations extends to the entire framework of electrodynamics. We can generalize the changing in these forms by proving the inconvenience of the form of only one of these four equations, and then to electrodynamics in general.

For simplicity, let the charge in the primed frame move only in the x-direction, while being subjected in a plane electromagnetic wave of electric field in the y-direction $\vec{E} = E(x, t)\vec{j}$, and a magnetic field in the z-direction $\vec{B} = B(x, t)\vec{k}$, then the left-hand side of equation 29 becomes:

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \begin{vmatrix} i & j & k \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \\ 0 & 0 & B \end{vmatrix} = -\frac{\partial B}{\partial x} \vec{j}$$

hence, the fourth equation in the case of our simple study will reduce to be:

$$\frac{\partial B}{\partial x} = -\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} \quad (30)$$

which indicates that the magnetic field and electric field components are perpendicular to each other and to the direction of propagation.

Moreover, Lorentz force affecting on will be calculated as:

$$\vec{f} = qE \vec{j} + q \begin{vmatrix} i & j & k \\ v_q & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & B \end{vmatrix}$$

$$\therefore \vec{f} = q(E - v_q B) \vec{j} \quad (31)$$

and we know previously that force is invariant under Galilean transformations, hence:

$$\therefore \vec{f}' = q(E' - v'_q B') \vec{j} \quad , \quad \text{where} \quad v_q = v'_q + v \quad (32)$$

from equations 31 and 32:

$$E' - v'_q B' = E - (v'_q + v)B$$

$$\therefore E = E' + vB \quad (33)$$

$$\therefore B = B' \quad (34)$$

we have to involve both x' and t' in our calculations via the chain rule in order to transfer equation 30 to the primed frame, since magnetic field is a function of both position and time

$$\frac{\partial B}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial B}{\partial x'} \cdot \frac{\partial x'}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial B}{\partial t'} \cdot \frac{\partial t'}{\partial x}$$

$$\therefore \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial B}{\partial x'}$$

from equation 34

$$\frac{\partial B}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial B'}{\partial x'} \quad (36)$$

to convert the right hand side we start with:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial x'} \cdot \frac{\partial x'}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial E}{\partial t'} \cdot \frac{\partial t'}{\partial t}$$

$$\therefore \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial t'} - v \frac{\partial E}{\partial x'}$$

from equation 33

$$\therefore \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial E'}{\partial t'} + v \frac{\partial B'}{\partial t'} - v \frac{\partial E'}{\partial x'} - v^2 \frac{\partial B'}{\partial x'}$$

Hence, equation 30 in the primed frame will have the form of

$$\frac{\partial B'}{\partial x'} = -\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial E'}{\partial t'} - \frac{1}{c^2} \left(v \frac{\partial B'}{\partial t'} - v \frac{\partial E'}{\partial x'} - v^2 \frac{\partial B'}{\partial x'} \right)$$

which clearly varies from one frame to another, leading to infinite forms of these relations according to infinite inertial frames, i.e. according to Galilean relativistic mechanics; laws of electrodynamics are frame-dependent, and that violates principles of spatial relativity, where all the laws of physics must be invariant in all inertial frames.

The solution to this issue in special relativity is the unification of electric and magnetic fields, where magnetic and electric fields have no separate meaning. Instead, we have a single concept of electromagnetic fields, which is the interdependence between them, a field of purely electric, or purely magnetic components to an observer in one frame can have both electric and magnetic components in another frame, which is clear to be the solution of the charge paradox mentioned before.

This effect is clearly due to the relativistic charge density[3] between the two frames given as

$$\rho = \frac{\rho_o}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{u^2}{c^2}}}$$

which mainly affects on the detected electric field, according to Maxwell's first relation 26, moreover, different current density, where $J = \rho u$, causing in the detection of different magnetic field, and this is obvious from the fourth relation 29, where the relativistic current density[3] will be:

$$\vec{J} = \frac{\rho_o \vec{u}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{u^2}{c^2}}}$$

A simple example[3] can illustrate this idea, if an observer is observing a positively charged particle moving with a relativistic velocity u near by a wire carrying a stream of electrons of drift velocity v in the opposite direction, according to his frame of reference, the wire has equivalent positive and negative charge density, and the wire is neutral. On the other hand, the current density due to the negatively charged electrons is non-zero. Hence, according to his frame of reference, the moving charge is deflecting towards the wire according to a generated magnetic field by the current flowing through.

Figure 18: Different reasons of motion relative to different points of view

According to the positive charge, the electrons stream is moving with velocity $-u$, hence the separation between electrons is contracted causing higher negative charge density due to the electrons than that of the positive cores, i.e. it becomes no longer electrically neutral and the charge will explain its attraction towards the wire as the impact of the electric field around the relatively charged wire.

Now, one observer explained the deflection to be the impact of the magnetic field component of Lorentz force, and the other in the charge frame explained it as the impact of the electric field term.

In short, electric and magnetic fields are not absolute quantities, instead they are frame-dependent components leading to electric-like, magnetic-like or electromagnetic waves-like, according to different frames.

5.1 Potential and current four-vectors

Potential four-vector is an element combines the electric and magnetic potentials basically depending on the current four-vector, since current and charge are not anymore two independent quantities in relativity, where the current four-vector[3] has the form:

$$J^\mu = (J^0, J^1, J^2, J^3) \quad (38)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} J^\mu &= (c\rho, J^x, J^y, J^z) = \rho_o\gamma(c, v_x, v_y, v_z) \\ \therefore J^\mu &= \rho_o U^\mu \end{aligned}$$

And it is clear from this form that the it can be considered as a four-vector, where it is nothing but a scalar invariant quantity (the rest charge density) times the velocity four-vector

$$\begin{aligned} U'^\mu &= \Lambda_\nu^\mu U^\nu \\ \rho_o U'^\mu &= \Lambda_\nu^\mu \rho_o U^\nu \\ J'^\mu &= \Lambda_\nu^\mu J^\nu \end{aligned}$$

it follows that the temporal component causes the electric potential caused by static charges, and the spatial components are the magnetic potential sources generated by electrical current $A^\mu = (\frac{\phi}{c}, A^x, A^y, A^z)$ where the factor c is added to balance dimensions. Then, the potential four-vector is set in the form of

$$A^\mu = (A^0, A^1, A^2, A^3)$$

In so called the inhomogeneous wave equation, $\square^2 A^\mu = \mu_0 J^\mu$, which has got this naming since the D'Alembertian operator[3] has the same form of that in the wave equation, $\square^2 = -\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} + \nabla^2$ constructed of both the time and position second derivatives.

it is clear that the potential can be indeed set as a four-vector, as it can be set as some scalars multiplied by the current four-vector, then:

$$\begin{aligned} A'^\mu &= \Lambda_\nu^\mu A^\nu \quad (39) \\ \begin{pmatrix} A'^0 \\ A'^1 \\ A'^2 \\ A'^3 \end{pmatrix} &= \begin{pmatrix} \gamma & -\beta\gamma & 0 & 0 \\ -\beta\gamma & \gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} A^0 \\ A^1 \\ A^2 \\ A^3 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

From this final relation, it follows that the electric and magnetic potentials in the primed frame are dependent on the electric and magnetic potentials in the other system, hence, the pure electric field in one system can indeed be observed as pure magnetic field in another.

5.2 Electromagnetic field tensor

It is the geometric object combining electric and magnetic fields in spacetime, unifying their impact on a charge in spacetime, instead of separating their influence.

According to vector calculus, gradient of curl is zero, where there is no outflow of a circulating field, i.e. from Maxwell's second equation 27, the magnetic field must be the curl of some quantity, which must be the potential for dimensions balance

$$B = \nabla \times A \quad (40)$$

then, the third equation 28 can be set as

$$\nabla \times E = -\nabla \times \frac{\partial A}{\partial t}$$

since for static charges $\nabla \times E = 0$, and the curl of the gradient of scalar quantities is zero

$$\therefore E = -\nabla\phi \quad \text{and} \quad \nabla \times \left(E + \frac{\partial A}{\partial t} \right) = 0$$

$$\therefore \nabla \times \left(E + \frac{\partial A}{\partial t} \right) = \nabla \times (-\nabla\phi)$$

$$\therefore E = -\nabla\phi - \frac{\partial A}{\partial t} \quad (41)$$

where this relation refers to the total electric field produced due to the change in potential around the charge, and due to the change of the magnetic field potential with respect to time.

From equation 41, and by defining the derivative four-vector $\partial^\nu = (\partial^0, \partial^1, \partial^2, \partial^3) = \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}, -\frac{\partial}{\partial x}, -\frac{\partial}{\partial y}, -\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right)$ we get:

$$-\frac{E_x}{c} = \partial^0 A^1 - \partial^1 A^0 \quad (42)$$

$$-\frac{E_y}{c} = \partial^0 A^2 - \partial^2 A^0 \quad (43)$$

$$-\frac{E_z}{c} = \partial^0 A^3 - \partial^3 A^0 \quad (44)$$

from equation 40:

$$-B_x = \partial^2 A^3 - \partial^3 A^2 \quad (45)$$

$$-B_y = \partial^3 A^1 - \partial^1 A^3 \quad (46)$$

$$-B_z = \partial^1 A^2 - \partial^2 A^1 \quad (47)$$

from equations 42 : 47, it follows that we can set all of these equations in a rank-2 anti-symmetric tensor

$$F^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\frac{E_x}{c} & -\frac{E_y}{c} & -\frac{E_z}{c} \\ \frac{E_x}{c} & 0 & -B_z & B_y \\ \frac{E_y}{c} & B_z & 0 & -B_x \\ \frac{E_z}{c} & -B_y & B_x & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (48)$$

which is known as the electromagnetic field tensor which unifies both the electric and magnetic field, and can be set as an equation in the form of

$$F^{\mu\nu} = \partial^\mu A^\nu - \partial^\nu A^\mu \quad (49)$$

5.3 Maxwell relations compact form

It was found that the Maxwell's four equations can be compressed in only two equations[3] depending on the electromagnetic field tensor and the current-four vector

$$\partial_\mu F^{\mu\nu} = \mu_o J^\nu \quad (50)$$

$$\partial_\mu \tilde{F}^{\mu\nu} = 0 \quad (51)$$

where $\partial_\mu = \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} = (\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial}{\partial z})$ and $\tilde{F}^{\mu\nu}$ is the dual electromagnetic field tensor

$$\tilde{F}^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -B_x & -B_y & -B_z \\ B_x & 0 & \frac{E_z}{c} & -\frac{E_y}{c} \\ B_y & -\frac{E_z}{c} & 0 & \frac{E_x}{c} \\ B_z & \frac{E_y}{c} & -\frac{E_x}{c} & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

which is expressed by Levi-Civita tensor.

If we set $\nu = 0$, and substituted in the first equation 50 (the inhomogeneous equation), we conclude to Maxwell's first equation 26, and if we set $\nu = [1 : 3]$ and carry out the substitution, we obtain the fourth relation 29.

On the other hand, by the substitution in the in homogeneous equation 51 by $\nu = 0$, we get the second equation 27, and finally, if we set $\nu = [1 : 3]$, the relation will reduce to the Maxwell's third relation 28.

5.4 Lorentz invariant of Maxwell's equations

By proving that the two equations 50 and 51 obey Lorentz transformation, we can directly conclude that Maxwell's four relations have the same form in all inertial frames.

Since $x'^\alpha = \Lambda_\beta^\alpha x^\beta$, then $dx'^\alpha = \Lambda_\beta^\alpha dx^\beta$

$$\therefore \Lambda_\beta^\alpha = \frac{dx'^\alpha}{dx^\beta} \quad (52)$$

and the inverse transformation will be

$$\therefore \Lambda_\gamma^\beta = \frac{dx^\beta}{dx'^\gamma} \quad (53)$$

where $\delta_\gamma^\alpha = \Lambda_\beta^\alpha \Lambda_\gamma^\beta$ which behaves as an identity matrix, where it is nothing but the combination between the transformation and its inverse.

From the chain rule

$$\partial'_\nu = \frac{\partial}{\partial x'^\nu} = \frac{\partial x^\gamma}{\partial x'^\nu} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\gamma} = \Lambda_\nu^\gamma \partial_\gamma \quad (54)$$

using equations 39 to carry out transformation on equation 49

$$\begin{aligned} F'^{\mu j} &= \Lambda_i^\mu \Lambda_k^j (\partial'^i A'^k - \partial'^k A'^i) \\ F'^{\mu j} &= \Lambda_i^\mu \Lambda_k^j F^{ik} \end{aligned} \quad (55)$$

then, the primed version of the first compact relation 50 can be transferred as

$$\begin{aligned} \partial'_\mu F'^{\mu j} &= \mu_o J'^j \\ \Lambda_\mu^\gamma \partial_\gamma \Lambda_i^\mu \Lambda_k^j F^{ik} &= \mu_o \Lambda_\tau^j J^\tau \\ \delta_i^\gamma \partial_\gamma \Lambda_k^j F^{ik} &= \mu_o \Lambda_\tau^j J^\tau \\ \delta_i^\gamma \partial_\gamma \Lambda_j^\pi \Lambda_k^j F^{ik} &= \mu_o \Lambda_j^\pi \Lambda_\tau^j J^\tau \\ \partial_\gamma \delta_i^\gamma \delta_k^\pi F^{ik} &= \mu_o \delta_\tau^\pi J^\tau \\ \partial_\gamma F^{\gamma\pi} &= \mu_o J^\pi \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

which indeed has the same form in the unprimed frame.

The second relation 51 will be transferred as

$$\begin{aligned} \partial'_\alpha \tilde{F}'^{\alpha\beta} &= 0 \\ \Lambda_\alpha^i \partial_i \Lambda_\mu^\alpha \Lambda_\nu^\beta \tilde{F}^{\mu\nu} &= 0 \\ \delta_\mu^i \partial_i \Lambda_\beta^j \Lambda_\nu^\beta \tilde{F}^{\mu\nu} &= 0 \\ \partial_i \delta_\mu^i \delta_\nu^j \tilde{F}^{\mu\nu} &= 0 \\ \therefore \partial_i \tilde{F}^{ij} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (57)$$

which has the same form in the primed frame.

from equations 56 and 57, we conclude that Maxwell's equations have the same form in all frames under Lorentz transformation, and then for sure all the laws of electrodynamics will be.

6 Conclusion

In this article, we discussed the necessity of a more generalized framework that describes the mechanics at speeds comparable to the speed of light, namely special relativity, which one of whose postulates that all the laws of physics have the same form in all inertial frames, and that was mathematically verified in this study for the laws of kinematics, dynamics, and electrodynamics such as Maxwell's equations. We hope to apply this framework in the subatomic and astronomical domains.

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